

Bridge Monitoring and Independence Testing for Locally Stationary Processes

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Abstract

Sensor data of monitoring systems of an infrastructural building is used to identify or even predict defects on the structure. Nevertheless, there are several conditions which influence the sensor output, from said defects over non-defecting events up to simple environmental changes. Therefore, most monitoring systems measure environmental parameters as well. To figure out which external phenomenon influences the sensor data gathered directly on the structure, this paper proposes a testing procedure tailor-made for locally stationary processes as those are well-suited to model such data. The test uses a weighted distance and its empirical version, which rely on the behavior of joint characteristic functions in the presence of independence. Moreover, a bootstrap analogue of these distances enables the testing procedure's compilation. Subsequently, a simulation study illustrates the general working of the test. Afterwards, the method is applied to real sensor data originating from structural health monitoring of a concrete bridge to identify dependencies between different sensor outputs.

Key Words: Independence testing, non-parametric, local stationarity, bootstrap

1. Introduction

To compensate for time- and cost-intensive human on-site inspection of infrastructural buildings, more and more monitoring systems are installed. Since these monitoring systems work with different sensor types, differentiation between environmental effects and actual defects of the structure, which both have an influence on the sensor data, is an important aspect of the output interpretation. In cases where the behavior of this data is explicable by environmental effects, there is no indication of an alteration in the structure's behavior. Ideally, sensor output data can be explained and predicted by environmental data such as temperature via regression. However, this is not always an option, and there is often a lack of explicit formulas. Then, a comparison of the behavior of environmental and sensor data can help to recognize similarities. For this purpose, a classical approach would be the observation of the correlation. Nevertheless, this is only useful to capture linear dependencies. To broaden the possible dependence structures to be detected, the use of a weighted distance based on the characteristic function (CF) as it can be found in Beering (2021) is proposed instead. Additionally, it is tailor-made for locally stationary processes. This class of stochastic processes is highly suitable to describe the data originating from both the structure and the environment.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the testing procedure. It starts with a brief recapitulation of the concept of local stationarity, displays necessary regularity conditions and illustrates the concept of the weighted distance. Moreover, it shows the need for a bootstrap counterpart and provides a suitable bootstrap algorithm. For the sake of notational simplicity, this paper is restricted to the one-dimensional case. Ensuing, in Section 3, a simulation study shows the general effect of the proposed testing procedure. Finally, the test is used on real-world monitoring data. Afterwards, Section 4 concludes with a roundup and outlook.

2. Testing Procedure

2.1 Theory of the Real World

The concept of locally approximating non-stationary processes by stationary ones was introduced by Dahlhaus (1997). In the following, we focus on linear locally stationary processes. To this end, let $(X_{t,T})_{t=1}^T$, $T \in \mathbb{N}$, be a linear, time-varying process of the following form:

$$X_{t,T} = \mu\left(\frac{t}{T}\right) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} a_{t,T}(j) \varepsilon_{t-j}$$

with a mean function $\mu(\cdot)$, coefficients $(a_{t,T}(j))$ and innovations (ε_t) . Then, under certain assumptions, there exists a strong strictly stationary process $(\widetilde{X}_t(u))$ with

$$\widetilde{X}_t(u) = \mu(u) + \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} a(u, j) \varepsilon_{t-j},$$

which is the local approximation of $X_{t,T}$ in a neighborhood of a fixed time point $u = \frac{t}{T}$. Note that both the mean function as well as the innovation process stay unchanged. Only the coefficients $(a(u, j))$ in the definition of $X_{t,T}$ differ from those composing $\widetilde{X}_t(u)$. The necessary regularity conditions to allow for this local approximation read as follows:

Assumption 1.

- i. *The innovations are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.), centered and have $\left(\frac{2+\delta}{2}\right)$ -th absolute moments for some $\delta \in \left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right)$.*
- ii. *The coefficients decay exponentially and are sufficiently smooth over time.*
- iii. *The coefficients $a_{t,T}(j)$ and $a\left(\frac{t}{T}, j\right)$ are adequately close.*
- iv. *The mean function is continuously differentiable.*

A more detailed description can be found in Beering (2021). Now, we address the question whether two locally stationary processes are index-wisely independent or not. To find an answer, a weighted distance based on the CF proposed in Beering (2021) is consulted. This distance is inspired by the concept of distance covariance introduced by Székely et al. (2007) and its modification for locally stationary processes by Jentsch et al. (2020). For this purpose, consider two locally stationary processes $(Y_{t,T})$ and $(Z_{t,T})$ with corresponding companion processes $(\widetilde{Y}_t(u))$ and $(\widetilde{Z}_t(u))$, respectively. For fixed $u \in [0, 1]$, we aim to test for

$$\mathcal{H}_0: \widetilde{Y}_0(u) \text{ and } \widetilde{Z}_0(u) \text{ being independent} \quad \text{versus} \quad \mathcal{H}_1: \widetilde{Y}_0(u) \text{ and } \widetilde{Z}_0(u) \text{ being dependent},$$

as, with T tending to infinity, the result can be transferred to the locally stationary processes. For $s_1, s_2 \in \mathbb{R}$, the characteristic functions belonging to the companion processes are of the following form:

$$\varphi_Y(u; s_1) := E e^{is_1 \widetilde{Y}_0(u)} \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi_Z(u; s_2) := E e^{is_2 \widetilde{Z}_0(u)}.$$

In consequence, the joint characteristic function of $\widetilde{Y}_0(u)$ and $\widetilde{Z}_0(u)$ is written as

$$\varphi_{Y,Z}(u; s_1, s_2) := E e^{is_1 \widetilde{Y}_0(u) + is_2 \widetilde{Z}_0(u)}.$$

With a positive weight function $w(\cdot, \cdot)$, the weighted CF-based distance according to Beering (2021) is defined as

$$\mathfrak{C}_{Y,Z}(u) := \int_{\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}} |\varphi_{Y,Z}(u; s_1, s_2) - \varphi_Y(u; s_1)\varphi_Z(u; s_2)|^2 w(s_1, s_2) ds_1 ds_2.$$

To ensure the integrability of the integrand above, the weight function is assumed to decrease sufficiently fast on the edges. A possible choice would be

$$w(s_1, s_2) = e^{-(|s_1|^2 + |s_2|^2)},$$

which will be used in the simulations in the following section. Contrary to the distance covariance of Székely et al. (2007), our choice for w is integrable. For further explanation, see Beering (2021). Independently of the particular choice for the weight function, the function itself has to be always positive. Therefore, $\mathfrak{C}_{Y,Z}(u)$ becomes 0 if and only if the joint CF equals the product of the individual CFs, that is if $\tilde{Y}_0(u)$ and $\tilde{Z}_0(u)$ are independent. In other words, the unique capability of detecting independence of the CF is transferred to $\mathfrak{C}_{Y,Z}(u)$. However, in a testing scenario, we deal with observations $Y_{1,T}, \dots, Y_{T,T}$ and $Z_{1,T}, \dots, Z_{T,T}$ of the locally stationary processes in lieu of the respective companion processes. Thus, we are in need for an empirical counterpart to $\mathfrak{C}_{Y,Z}(u)$, which we obtain by replacing the CFs used to define $\mathfrak{C}_{Y,Z}(u)$ by their local observation analogues. With the help of a kernel function K and a bandwidth b_T , we get

$$\widehat{\varphi}_Y(u; s_1) := \frac{1}{b_T T} \sum_{t=1}^T K\left(\frac{\frac{t}{T} - u}{b_T}\right) e^{is_1 Y_{t,T}}$$

and

$$\widehat{\varphi}_Z(u; s_2) := \frac{1}{b_T T} \sum_{t=1}^T K\left(\frac{\frac{t}{T} - u}{b_T}\right) e^{is_2 Z_{t,T}}$$

as well as

$$\widehat{\varphi}_{Y,Z}(u; s_1, s_2) := \frac{1}{b_T T} \sum_{t=1}^T K\left(\frac{\frac{t}{T} - u}{b_T}\right) e^{is_1 Y_{t,T} + is_2 Z_{t,T}}.$$

Consequently, the empirical weighted CF-based distance reads as

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}(u) := \int_{\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}} |\widehat{\varphi}_{Y,Z}(u; s_1, s_2) - \widehat{\varphi}_Y(u; s_1)\widehat{\varphi}_Z(u; s_2)|^2 w(s_1, s_2) ds_1 ds_2$$

using the same weight function w as before. In order for $\widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}(u)$ to be a suitable replacement for $\mathfrak{C}_{Y,Z}(u)$, the kernel function and bandwidth are to meet the following requirements:

Assumption 2.

- i. The kernel $K: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is symmetric, nonnegative and Lipschitz-continuous.
- ii. It holds $\int K(u) du = 1$, and K has the compact support $[-1, 1]$.
- iii. The bandwidth sequence (b_T) is nonnegative and fulfills $T b_T^{\frac{4+\delta}{2}} = \mathcal{O}(1)$ for $\delta \in \left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right)$.

Equipped with all essential assumptions, we are now able to state the main theorem, which displays both the necessary convergence as well as divergence to build our testing procedure upon:

Theorem 1.

Let Assumptions 1 and 2 be fulfilled. Additionally, assume $\tilde{Y}_0(u)$ and $\tilde{Z}_0(u)$ to be

- i. independent. Then, it holds for fixed $u \in [0,1]$

$$b_T T \widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}(u) \xrightarrow{d} \int_{\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}} |G(u; s_1, s_2)|^2 w(s_1, s_2) ds_1 ds_2,$$

where $(G(u; s_1, s_2))_{(s_1, s_2) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}}$ is a centered Gaussian process with continuous paths.

- ii. dependent. Then, we have for fixed $u \in [0,1]$

$$b_T T \widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}(u) \xrightarrow{P} \infty.$$

As already mentioned, the two parts of Theorem 1 pertaining different convergence behavior lead the way for our testing procedure. More precisely, by determining a suitable threshold K_p in dependence of the desired testing level p with the aid of quantiles, the testing result should reject the null hypothesis, that is independence of $\tilde{Y}_0(u)$ and $\tilde{Z}_0(u)$, if K_p is exceeded. However, the threshold K_p cannot be deduced right away. This can be seen in a more detailed version of Theorem 1 in Beering (2021), where also the proof is provided. There, it becomes clear that the covariance function of the resulting Gaussian process relies on the companion processes. As these are not observable, a bootstrap procedure is required to conduct the test.

2.2 A Bootstrap Counterpart

The basic bootstrap approach means drawing with replacement from a sample. In doing so, it is not possible to represent the dependence structure of the original sample correctly. To solve this issue, Dowla et al. (2013) proposed the so-called local block bootstrap (LBB) for trend estimation for locally stationary processes. This bootstrap method uses local selection, where the blocks are chosen in a way their indices are close to the ones of the corresponding blocks of the original process. More precisely, a block of length L_T is replaced by a block of the same length, whose indices are shifted by a random number. The idea is to use the existing algorithm with adjusted assumptions to suit our scenario. The LBB algorithm reads as follows:

Algorithm 1 (Bootstrap algorithm).

- 1) Consider a blocklength L_T depending on T .
 - a) Select a window parameter $D_T \in (0,1)$ such that $T D_T \in \mathbb{N}$.
 - b) Generate i.i.d. integers $k_0, \dots, k_{\lfloor T/L_T \rfloor - 1}$ using a discrete uniform distribution on $[-T D_T, T D_T]$.
 - c) Define $X_{1,T}^*, \dots, X_{T,T}^*$ via

$$X_{j+iL_T,T}^* := X_{j+iL_T+k_i,T}$$

for $j = 1, \dots, L_T$, $i = 0, \dots, \lfloor \frac{T}{L_T} \rfloor - 1$.

- d) Construct the bootstrap estimator by replacing $X_{t,T}$ with $X_{t,T}^*$
- 2) If a chosen index i of a block lays outside of $[1, T]$, use $-k_i$ instead of k_i for the whole block.

The second part of Algorithm 1 preserves the interrelated dependence structure and, in addition to that, ensures no observation is used twice in the same block. Note that the generating distribution for $k_0, \dots, k_{\lfloor T/L_T \rfloor - 1}$ does not have to be a discrete uniform distribution. Nevertheless, it corresponds to the original block bootstrap algorithm for stationary processes. In order to use the proposed algorithm for our scenario, we need to impose some requirements to the bootstrap parameters:

Assumption 3.

For blocklength L_T and window parameter D_T , it holds

- i. $L_T = o\left((b_T T)^{\frac{\delta}{2(1+\delta)}}\right)$ and
- ii. $(b_T T)^{\frac{2\delta}{2+\delta}} \leq TD_T \leq (b_T T)^{\frac{1}{2+\delta}}$,
respectively.

Now we can establish a bootstrap counterpart to the empirical weighted CF-based distance, that is

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}^*(u) = & \int_{\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}} \left| \widehat{\varphi}_{Y,Z}^*(u; s_1, s_2) - E^* \widehat{\varphi}_{Y,Z}^*(u; s_1, s_2) E^* \widehat{\varphi}_Y^*(u; s_1) E^* \widehat{\varphi}_Z^*(u; s_2) \right. \\ & \left. - \widehat{\varphi}_Y^*(u; s_1) \widehat{\varphi}_Z^*(u; s_2) \right|^2 w(s_1, s_2) ds_1 ds_2 \end{aligned}$$

with

$$\widehat{\varphi}_{Y,Z}^*(u; s_1, s_2) := \frac{1}{b_T T} \sum_{t=1}^T K\left(\frac{\frac{t}{T} - u}{b_T}\right) e^{is_1 Y_{t,T}^* + is_2 Z_{t,T}^*}$$

as well as

$$\widehat{\varphi}_Y^*(u; s_1) := \frac{1}{b_T T} \sum_{t=1}^T K\left(\frac{\frac{t}{T} - u}{b_T}\right) e^{is_1 Y_{t,T}^*}$$

and

$$\widehat{\varphi}_Z^*(u; s_2) := \frac{1}{b_T T} \sum_{t=1}^T K\left(\frac{\frac{t}{T} - u}{b_T}\right) e^{is_2 Z_{t,T}^*}$$

provided by the LBB. Note that $\widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}^*(u)$ contains bootstrap expectations which do not have a visible counterpart in the definition of $\widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}(u)$. However, their real-world counterparts would cancel themselves out. This explains their absence in the definition of $\widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}(u)$. Next, we formulate a bootstrap version of Theorem 1:

Theorem 2.

Under the same assumptions as in Theorem 1 plus the fulfillment of Assumption 3, it holds for fixed $u \in [0,1]$

$$b_T T \widehat{\mathfrak{C}}_{Y,Z}^*(u) \xrightarrow{d} \int_{\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}} |G(u; s_1, s_2)|^2 w(s_1, s_2) ds_1 ds_2$$

in P -probability, where $(G(u; s_1, s_2))_{(s_1, s_2) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}}$ is a centered Gaussian process with continuous paths and the same covariance function as in Theorem 1.

Again, we see dissimilarities between Theorem 1 and 2, as the latter only consists of one result instead of two. The cause thereof can be found in the counterpart of the CF in the bootstrap world. More precisely, the equality between the joint CF and the product of the marginal CFs under independence cannot be transferred to the bootstrap expectations of the bootstrap version of the ECFs. Hence, the need for presupposed independence is obsolete. Consequently, Theorem 2 holds whether the companion processes, and thus the appurtenant locally stationary ones, are independent or not. Moreover, the concomitant absence of divergence allows for the use of the bootstrap results

in our testing procedure since the empirical bootstrap quantile will always mimic the one belonging to the independent real-world case. Thus, the quantile established via the LBB provides the threshold we were looking for.

3. Simulations and Real-world Example

3.1 Simulation Study

The theory established above is now brought to a test via a simulation study as well as a real-data example. Beginning with the simulation study, consider two time-varying auto-regressive processes of order 1, namely $(Y_{t,T})$ and $(Z_{t,T})$, defined as

$$Y_{t,T} = \begin{cases} 0.9 \sin\left(2\pi \frac{1}{T}\right) \varepsilon_{Y,0} + \varepsilon_{Y,1}, & t = 1, \\ 0.9 \sin\left(2\pi \frac{t}{T}\right) Y_{t-1,T} + \varepsilon_{Y,t}, & t = 2, \dots, T, \end{cases}$$

and

$$Z_{t,T} = \begin{cases} 0.9 \sin\left(2\pi \frac{1}{T}\right) \varepsilon_{Z,0} + \varepsilon_{Z,1}, & t = 1, \\ 0.9 \sin\left(2\pi \frac{t}{T}\right) Z_{t-1,T} + \varepsilon_{Z,t}, & t = 2, \dots, T. \end{cases}$$

The innovation series $(\varepsilon_{Y,t})$ and $(\varepsilon_{Z,t})$ are i.i.d and have the same marginal distribution. It is obvious that the processes $(Y_{t,T})$ and $(Z_{t,T})$ are t -wisely independent if the belonging innovation processes are independent following the way the linear locally stationary processes are built. For the marginal distribution of the innovation series, an α -stable distribution with parameters $\alpha = 1.5$, $\mu = 0$, $\beta = 0$ and $\gamma = 0.5$ is chosen. An advantage of this broad class of distributions is the inheritance characteristic: If the innovations follow an α -stable distribution, they bequeath the distribution with unchanged parameters α and μ to the linear process they are used in. The adjusting screws of the simulation study are the number of observations and the bootstrap parameters, which, in turn, depend on the bandwidth b_T , see Assumption 3. In this simulation study, we have three different parameter sets A , B and C combined with four sample sizes from $T = 1000$ up to $T = 7500$. The number of outer loops is $N = 100$, whereas each loop contains $N_{BS} = 500$ bootstrap loops. Because independence is considered as the null hypothesis, the simulations yield non-rejection rates as results. With the significance level $p = 0.05$, the aim is a non-rejection rate of 0.95 under the null hypothesis. As it can be seen in Table 1, higher sample sizes lead to higher non-rejection rates, which come close to the desired 95-percent mark. A more detailed simulation study can be found in Beering (2021).

Table 1: Non-rejection rates for $p = 0.05$ based on independent innovation series for bootstrap parameter sets A , B and C

T	A	B	C
1000	0.76	0.76	0.81
2500	0.89	0.89	0.93
5000	0.95	0.91	0.95
7500	0.93	0.85	0.94

After having fed two independent locally stationary processes to the algorithm, we are lacking the dependent counterpart. To verify whether dependence can be detected as well, consider three different scenarios varying in the degree of dependence. To begin with, the two processes $(Y_{t,T})$ and $(Z_{t,T})$ are composed by the same innovation process as the most obvious form of dependence. The other two degrees of dependence rely also on the dependence structures of the innovations and are

inspired by Bakirov et al. (2006) and Székely et al. (2007). The first supposes $(\varepsilon_{Y,t})$ to follow a standard Gaussian distribution. Based on this, $(\varepsilon_{Z,t})$ is formed by

$$\varepsilon_{Z,t} := \log(\varepsilon_{Y,t}^2)$$

for all $t \in \mathbb{N}_0$. In the most complicated dependence scenario, $(\varepsilon_{Y,t})$ follows, again, a standard Gaussian distribution as well as an auxiliary innovation process (ε_t) . Moreover, independence between (ε_t) and $(\varepsilon_{Y,t})$ is assumed. Finally, $(\varepsilon_{Z,t})$ is assembly as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{Z,t} := \varepsilon_{Y,t}\varepsilon_t$$

for all $t \in \mathbb{N}_0$. The results, that is the non-rejection rates, for bootstrap parameter set A can be found in Table 2. In the first column, the original rates for underlying independence are displayed for comparison. As it can be seen, using the same innovation series leads to non-rejection rates of 0 percent for every tried sample size T . For the dependence based on the logarithm, it needs $T = 2500$ for the rate to drop to 0, whereas the most hidden dependence structure requires a sample size of $T = 7500$ for the same result. Nevertheless, even with the latter, the non-rejection rate is continuously decreasing while the sample size augments. In conclusion, the more indirect the dependence is, the higher the number of observations is needed for the test to reject the null hypothesis, which is as expected.

Table 2: Non-rejection rates for $\mathfrak{p} = 0.05$ based on independent and dependent innovation series

T	<i>independent</i>	$\varepsilon_{Y,t} = \varepsilon_{Z,t}$	$\varepsilon_{Z,t} = \log(\varepsilon_{Y,t}^2)$	$\varepsilon_{Z,t} = \varepsilon_{Y,t}\varepsilon_t$
1000	0.76	0	0.21	0.59
2500	0.89	0	0	0.27
5000	0.95	0	0	0.05
7500	0.93	0	0	0

3.2 Real-data Example

With our real-data example, we go back to our initial question of identifying influential changes apart from defects in bridge monitoring. For that purpose, data from the project SFB 823, B5 of the German Research Foundation is used. This data was generated on a 1961-built concrete bridge for vehicles in Bochum, Germany, and the monitoring included crack widths at sixteen different locations as well as environmental and bridge temperatures. For a detailed description of the monitoring process, see Heinrich et al. (2021). Figure 1 displays the progress of the width of three different cracks in the first rows alongside two temperature profiles in the last rows.

Figure 1: Crack width at three different locations and two temperature profiles from a concrete bridge in Bochum, Germany

We like to answer the question whether the null hypothesis of independence can be rejected for the last four time series in combination with the crack width named WNN2 and shown in the first row. It turns out that the test rejects the null hypothesis for all but the last time series, see Table 3. This is as expected as changes in temperature lead to expansion or contraction of the concrete and, thus, the cracks. Whether we look at the comparably small crack WON2 in the second row or the large one, WON4, displayed in the third row, the temperature is the combining factor which influences all crack sizes leading to a joint dependent behavior of the two cracks WON2 and WON4 with WNN2. However, the rejection by testing the crack width in the first row together with the temperature in the fourth row is no surprise either due to said explanation. Nevertheless, the last row depicts a temperature profile from the future from the point of view of the profile of WNN2 in the first row. Hence, a dependence of any kind is impossible, which is why the outcome of the testing procedure makes sense. Recapitulatory, the testing procedure gave the expected results in both the dependent and the independent case.

Table 3: Results of the test for independence for $p = 0.05$ based on the processes of Figure 1

<i>WWN2</i>	<i>Rejection</i>	<i>Non-rejection</i>
WON2	\times	✓
WON4	\times	✓
Concurrent temperature	\times	✓
Shifted temperature	✓	\times

4. Conclusion and Outlook

The proposed testing procedure is a useful method to look for independence in sensor data. Hereby, we are not limited to linear dependence or stationarity, as the used distance is tailor-made for locally stationary processes. This opens a wide field of possible applications with sensor data emitted by natural phenomena. Theoretical and practical examples displayed the usefulness of the proposed procedure. Thanks to its ability to help overcoming existing challenges in the maintenance of infrastructure, this work offers starting points for interdisciplinary research. However, expanding the test for periods of time instead of time points is a natural extension, which will be part of a future publication.

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References

- Bakirov, N.K., Rizzo, M.L., and Székely, G.J. (2006). A multivariate nonparametric test of independence. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis* **97**, 1742-1756.
- Beering, C. (2021). A Functional Central Limit Theorem and Its Bootstrap Analogue for Locally Stationary Processes with Application to Independence Testing, PhD thesis, Technische Universität Braunschweig.
- Dahlhaus, R. (1997). Fitting time series models to nonstationary processes. *The Annals of Statistics* **25**, 1-37.
- Dowla, A., Paparoditis, E. and Politis, D.N. (2013). Local block bootstrap inference for trending time series. *Metrika* **76**, 733-764.
- Heinrich, J., Maurer, R., Leckey, K., Müller, C.H. and Ickstadt, K. (2021). Detektieren ermüdungsbedingter Spannstahlbrüche mittels Rissmonitoring im Versuch und am Bauwerk. *Bauingenieur* **96**(3).
- Jentsch, C., Leucht, A., Meyer, M. and Beering, C. (2020). Empirical characteristic functions-based estimation and distance correlation for locally stationary processes. *Journal of Time Series Analysis* **41**, 110-133.
- Székely, G. J., Rizzo, M.L. and Bakirov, N.K. (2007). Measuring and testing dependence by correlation of distances. *The Annals of Statistics* **35**, 2769-2794.